

Arzu Masim oglu Guliyev
Associate Professor of the Department of "Computer
Science" at the Azerbaijan State Pedagogical University
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A NEW MODEL OF EDUCATION USING COMPUTER TECHNOLOGY

Summary:

Each classification element has its purpose and characteristics. For example, the learning system corrects errors and shows the correct answer when learning any subject (subject) through a computer; analyzes the weaknesses of the learner in the subject area and develops tools to eliminate them; determines the amount, volume and degree of complexity of knowledge transfer depending on the degree of mastery. The article examines the creation of a structure for the management and methodological support system for improving knowledge and skills in accordance with the requirements of modern training.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence languages, prototype system development, educational software tools

Each classification element has its purpose and characteristics. For example, the learning system corrects errors and shows the correct answer when learning any subject (subject) through a computer; analyzes the weaknesses of the learner in the subject area and develops tools to eliminate them; determines the amount, volume and degree of complexity of knowledge transfer depending on the degree of mastery. The article examines the creation of a structure for the management and methodological support system for improving knowledge and skills in accordance with the requirements of modern training. The introduction of information processes into the educational structure, the informatization of the educational process require new qualities from all educational workers. This, in turn, implies the acquisition of new skills and habits. The training and improvement of educational system employees in ICT includes the following:

- Restructuring the system for training pedagogical personnel for secondary schools taking into account the concept of informatization of education;
- Creation of a management and methodological support system for improving the knowledge and skills of educational system employees in the field of ICT. Development of appropriate programs for increasing the ICT literacy of various categories of educational workers (primary school teachers, subject teachers, school administration). The improvement of subject teachers should not be limited only to training in the use of ICT equipment, attention should also be paid to instilling practical skills for the integration of existing resources into the educational process;

- Organization of computer science teachers with the necessary level of training to conduct relevant computer literacy courses for other subject teachers in their schools;

- Adequately evaluate the work of subject teachers and computer science teachers who use ICT, develop a system for stimulating and motivating their activities;

- holding various competitions and competitions among subject teachers and taking their results into account in stimulation and motivational measures;

- developing more flexible programs for the improvement of informatics teachers;

- training trainers to accelerate the improvement process;

- creating relevant institutions - information and methodological centers - for the preparation and improvement of educational staff in the regions;

- ensuring regularity and systematicity in the process of improving educational staff in the field of ICT;

- introducing new specialties related to the informatization of education in the system of higher, secondary specialized and technical vocational education.

In this sense, let us note the development of a new model of modern training through Expert Training Systems and its determination. The creation of an Expert Training System is one of the important and important issues for the development of educational software tools.

An Expert Training System (ETS) is a complex software complex that collects and disseminates the scientific knowledge and experience of highly qualified specialists in the field of education and training, and enables them to be used by those with relatively little specialized knowledge.

User interface – a software complex that implements a dialogue between the user and the ETS in the process of entering a request and receiving a response.

Logical result block – a program that models the course of the expert's thoughts and ideas based on the information in the knowledge base.

Explanatory subsystem – a software complex that answers the following types of user questions: How was this or that recommendation made? Why did the system make such a decision? The first question shows

the full course of obtaining an opinion by showing all the relevant fragments of the knowledge base, and the second question refers to the judgment that preceded the result.

Intellectual editor of the knowledge base – a program that allows a knowledge engineer to create a knowledge base in a dialog mode. It includes a built-in menu system, a template for the knowledge representation language, a "help" mode, and other service tools that facilitate working with the base.

Each classification element has its purpose and characteristics. For example, a training system corrects errors and shows the correct answer when learning a subject (subject) through a computer; analyzes the weaknesses of the learner in the subject area and develops tools to eliminate them; determines the amount, volume and complexity of knowledge transfer depending on the degree of mastery. An example of such systems is the PROUST system for Pascal's training. They aggregate (adapt) standard application software envelopes (for example, mathematical statistics, linear programming or database management systems) and consist of software complexes that are tools for manipulating knowledge. Hybrid systems can be an intellectual superstructure for application software envelopes or a tool for solving complex problems related to expert knowledge. However, compared to autonomous ES, the development of hybrid systems is much more complicated. Because the connection of software envelopes with different methodologies creates a number of theoretical and applied problems.

Instrumental tools for the development of ES have also been created. They can be divided into 4 groups:

Traditional programming languages (C, C+, Basic, Small Talk, Fortran, etc.). They are mainly designed for numerical algorithms, and since they have limited capabilities for working with symbolic and log-

ical data, they require a lot of work from the programmer. However, these languages are well adapted to traditional machine architecture.

1) Artificial intelligence languages - the most widespread are Lisp and Prolog. Their universality is lower than that of traditional programming languages, but they have wide capabilities for working with symbolic and logical data. Special computers are created on the basis of artificial intelligence languages (for example, Lisp - machine). These languages are not used in the development of Expert training systems.

2) Special software tools - provide the development of educational programs at a higher level than artificial intelligence languages.

3) Shells (Оболочки, shells) - a shell is a ready-made version of an ES without a knowledge base. Shells eliminate the programming processes in the creation of ES. In this case, only a specialist (expert) working in the subject area is required to fill the knowledge base with real data. It is difficult to use overlays for library-informational knowledge bases. Because it is very difficult to model a number of processes (for example, summarizing, compiling a bibliographic and analytical review, etc.).

The technology of creating educational software tools and the exemplary technology of developing individual ETS for the entire education system are almost the same. Currently, experts divide the development of ETS into six consecutive logical stages:

- 1) Identification of problems in the educational field;
- 2) development of a prototype system;
- 3) bringing the ES development to the operational level;
- 4) evaluation of the expert training system;
- 5) system coordination;
- 6) system support.

Identification of the problem area and problems is important for all stages of ETS. The head of ETS, that is, the knowledge engineer, must identify the problem. If an unsuitable problem is chosen, it can lead to a loss of time and money. The knowledge necessary for solving the problem should also be stable, accurate and relatively permanent in nature and cover all related issues.

The development of a prototype system is a generalized version of ETS. A prototype system is a special project for checking the correctness and coding of facts, judgment strategies, relationships between objects and processes provided by an expert. The prototype project consists of dozens of rules, frames and examples.

Experimental methods of selecting (discovering) knowledge, as well as a direct live dialogue between a knowledge engineer and an expert, were explained. However, this is not the only method. Currently, methods of selecting (discovering) knowledge for creating knowledge bases are given:

For example, let's build a computer model for calculating the square root of odd numbers within the natural numbers 5 to 195.

1. Building the algorithm for the given problem
2. Implementing the program for the problem in the Pascal programming language

3. Implementing the compiled program on a computer

Since the algorithm is methodologically understandable in the form of a block diagram, let's compile it.


```

Program SF;
Uses crt;
Var x:integer;
S:real;
Begin S:=0;
For x:=5 to 195 do begin
If x mod 2 <> 0 then s:=sqrt(x);
Writeln ('s=',s);
End;
End.
  
```

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